

Transfer Learning Models for Plant Disease Detection

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Abstract—Digital image processing is a significant part of the Information Technology department as nearly all the multimedia data are captured, processed, presented and transmitted with the help of this technology. Prompt and accurate detection of plant infections is necessary for successful farming. Early diagnosis has been the most effective way of preventing waste of resources, which will then lead to more efficient and sustainable agriculture. The real problem is the detection and determination of the diseases within the countless plants in the different environmental conditions. The current study presents a plant disease detection model using a technique called transfer learning, which involves integrating VGG16 (Visual Geometry Group) is a architecture designed with Deep CNN (Convolutional Neural Network). Specifically, the system is implemented in Python, and the effectiveness of the model is examined through metrics, such as accuracy, precision, and recall.

Keywords—Image Processing, Information Technology, Plant disease, Agriculture, Transfer learning, VGG16, Deep CNN

I. INTRODUCTION

The problems of environmental variability and sustainable agriculture are intimately linked to the problem of protecting plants. Researchers suggest that climate change affects the growth stages and development patterns of microorganisms, leading to complications in plant health. One main concern is the increased transmission rate of plant diseases in the current environment compared to earlier conditions. Regions where local expertise is lacking to solve these problems are particularly vulnerable to emerging plant diseases[1]. Accurately detecting infected plants in a timely manner is critical for effective agriculture. Early detection helps prevent unnecessary waste of financial and other resources, thereby improving productivity. The main objective is to identify plant diseases in different climates before they spread, ensuring precise and early diagnosis. Many methods are used to diagnose plant diseases but some symptoms may not be immediately visible with their effects becoming apparent only later. To solve this, an advanced diagnostic system is proposed that relies on visual signs and symptoms to recognize diseases[2]. A CAD (Computer-Aided Diagnosis) system is designed to diagnose plant diseases based on observed and pictorial symptoms.

The term CVS (Computer Vision System) refers to a method that is frequently used in agricultural fields. This method proves valuable for sorting fruits and identifying food items. It works by processing images, classifying grains, diagnosing weeds, and performing other similar tasks[3].

Images are captured using digital cameras and many techniques are applied to process these images. Effective DIP (Digital Image Processing) systems, such as color analysis and thresholding, are implemented to detect plant disorders. Common plant problems such as viral, fungal and bacterial diseases, as well as early and late scorch, are frequently observed[4]. The images are processed in various stages to diagnose plant ailments, including image acquisition, preprocessing, segmentation, feature extraction and classification. Figure 1 show the general process used to diagnose plant disorders.

Fig.1 Plant Disease Detection based on Image Processing [5]

Each step of the method described to recognize plant infections is as follows:

The first step is image acquisition, during which a robust method for recognizing plant diseases is developed based on photos taken under specific environmental conditions such as lighting[6]. The dataset is produced using a variety of images with different resolutions, captured during the plant's growth phases. The second step involves applying various tasks to the images using pre-processing techniques to improve the image or isolate important information[7].

This includes methods for removing noise from images or other unwanted objects. When a photograph is cropped, unnecessary areas are removed and only the relevant portions remain. Thirdly, the significant process in crucial situations is of segmenting the pictures in order to localize and place the infected plants[8]. As a result, this process helps separate the significant information from the background and divides the image into many distinct, non-overlapping regions. RoI (Region of Interest) is used to recognize the leaf area that is affected. The main focus is on segmenting the infected leaf in images of that the diseased and healthy parts can be distinguished [9]. The raw input is converted into larger images for a classifier using the feature extraction procedure. Its main purpose is to reduce the size of large images in order to assess abstract features, which provide the numerical representation of the image, containing information for classifying the data, such as shape, texture, or color. In a real system, farming specialists typically plan the features that are important for extracting attributes over a long period of time[10]. The next step, known as image classification, focuses on classifying the images based on their objective features. The main focus is on developing and implementing the classifiers. A vector is produced in the output as a result of the most common method of feature extraction. A classifier is then used to map this vector to a confidence score[11]. Many techniques such as RF (Random Forest), KNN (K-Nearest Neighbour), SVM (Support Vector Machine) and others are used to categorize the images.

SVM is used to generate a hyperplane, where both positive and negative patterns contribute to the optimal choice made during the training process. The aim of this strategy is to maximize these parathion by isolating the initial samples from the later ones and increasing the distance between the two samples from the hyperplane[12]. This ensures precise classification of the objective. KNN is a well-known and straight forward method for data classification. In many cases, the outcomes produced by K-NN are considered promising. Moreover, by incorporating previous data into the standard method, this algorithm helps improve its performance[13]. The majority label is used to classify each unlabelled instance among its K-NNs in the training set. Different DT (Decision tree) techniques are integrated to generate a RF (Random Forest). A decision tree is then used to build a tree using the distinguishing properties for each level of the tree[14]. The guiding principles of this approach are crucial for handling large-scale data. The DT (Decision Tree) method is a powerful tool for efficiently classifying data. The main objective of this method is to use a tree structure to organize many conditions in order to select the data[15]. The number of trees is used to evaluate the accuracy of the model, leading to the successful classification of small datasets. An effective technique called LR (logistic regression) is used to eliminate certain weighted attribute collections from the data, complete the logs, and arrange them in a linear fashion[16]. LR is a discriminative classification technique frequently used to predict the probability of an event. The first step in achieving this is to transform the data into a logistic function.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

M. Sardogan et.al, (2018) proposed classifying and identifying diseases in tomato plant leaves by using an LVQ (Learning Vector Quantization) technique and a CNN (Conventional Neural Network) algorithm[17]. Images were

automatically categorized using CNN modeling following feature extraction. The many illnesses that were present in plant leaves were categorized using the color data. This system filtered three channels, according to RGB components. To train the network, the LVQ method employed the output feature vector from the convolutional section. The trials were conducted using an open-source dataset that contained four illness symptoms and 500 photos of tomato plant leaves. The test results showed that four different diseases on tomato leaves could be fast and accurately identified using the methods provided.

Adedaja et.al (2019) presented a deep learning-based method was introduced to identify plant diseases from leaf photos using TL (transfer learning)[18]. The method employed CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks) in combination with the NASNet architecture. This method was trained and tested on the PlantVillage dataset, which consists of numerous images of plant leaves with varying levels of disease and parasite infestation. The results of the experiment showed that the algorithm was able to effectively distinguish between healthy and diseased plant images. Furthermore, the algorithm achieved an accuracy of approximately 93.82%.

P. Jiang et.al (2019) developed an enhanced ConvNet (convolutional neural network) method to detect diseases in apple leaves[19]. Complex photos taken in labs and the field were compiled into a database called ALDD (Apple Leaf Disease Dataset). Using the GoogleLeNet inception structure and rainbow concatenation, a new Deep-CNN-based apple leaf disease detection system was generated. A dataset of 26,377 images of infectious apple leaves was used to train the INARSSD model to recognized apple leaf diseases. The proof of concept showed that the created algorithm generated 78.80% mAP.

P. Wspanialy, et.al (2020) created a unique artificial intelligence system to automatically detect many diseases, locate infections that had not been previously observed and evaluate the severity of infections on all leaves[20]. Proportional are measurements were the most effective way to measure the severity of bacterial and fungal diseases. Ordinal classes, however, were the most effective in treating a variety of systemic diseases caused by viruses and insects. In order to test and train the classifier model and demonstrate how many leaf properties impact disease identification, the study used the nine distinct tomato disease kinds from the Plant Village tomato dataset. Incorporating the model into a computerized measurement design can improve precision and green house coverage while reducing expenses and measuring bias.

Z. Iqbal, et.al (2018) presented in-depth taxonomy of citrus leaf diseases in the study[21]. The problems encountered at each stage of the process were first discussed, highlighting how these difficulties significantly impacted the accuracy of identification and classification tasks. The paper also presented an in-depth case study on automated disease detection and classification techniques. Furthermore, it explored many methods for pre-processing, segmentation, feature extraction, feature selection and classification. The findings of the case study showed that automated detection and classification of citrus plant infections were still in the early stages. To fully automate every step of disease identification and classification, additional tools needed to be incorporated.

A. Waheed, et.al (2020) discussed the development of DenseNet, an advanced dense CNN architecture, to recognize and categorize diseases in maize plants[22]. A method was proposed to monitor crop health using DL (deep learning). The accuracy of the proposed architecture was calculated to be 98.06%. Furthermore, this architecture required fewer computational resources compared to traditional ConvNets (Convolutional neural networks). The proposed design was evaluated against existing CNN architectures based on two performance metrics. The comparison revealed that the new architecture performed comparably to conventional ConvNet models.

S. Mishra, et.al (2020) proposed a useful DCNN-based technique for diagnosing maize plant leaf diseases in the study[23]. To improve the performance of the deep ConvNet (Convolutional neural network), pooling combinations and hyper parameters were adjusted on a system equipped with a GPU (Graphics processing unit). The system's metrics were also improved to make it suitable for real-time estimation. The proposed architecture, which had already been trained, was implemented by combining CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) hardware blocks from the Intel Movidius Neural Compute Stick with a Raspberry Pi3. The framework showed its effectiveness in detecting diseases in maize plant leaves, achieving an accuracy of approximately 88.46%.

Z. Lin, et.al (2019) developed a unified CNN (convolutional neural network), called the M-bCNN (Matrix- based convolutional neural network) to detect diseases in plants [24]. The main component of this model was the convolutional kernel matrix. The convolutional layers in this model were arranged in parallel as a matrix, which, unlike traditional plain networks, effectively increased the model's data streams, neurons and connection channels by incorporating additional metrics. To test the model, images of wheat leaf infections were used, with a dataset consisting of 16,652 photos collected in Shandong province, China. The developed architecture achieved a training accuracy of 96.5% and a test accuracy of 90.1%.

E. C. Tetila, et.al (2019) examined various network weights for the robotic detection of infections in soybean leaves[25]. These weights were assigned to images of many soybean plant leaves, which were captured directly from a small, low-cost UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle). Four deep neural network models were evaluated in the study to achieve high accuracy. A range of FT (fine-tuning) and transfer learning techniques were used to optimize performance. To solve the problem of overfitting, the network was trained using data augmentation and dropout techniques. The SLIC method was applied to segment high-altitude images of plant leaves. The dataset used in this study was generated from real-world flying experiments, and computer vision tools were utilized to test it. The results showed that the detection accuracy could be significantly improved by using fine-tuned technique.

X. Liu, et.al (2021) designed a new large-scale plant disease dataset, consisting of 220,592 images and 271 different plant disease categories[26]. To capture the degree of variation in each image patch, the weights of all split patches were first calculated based on the cluster distribution of these patches. Each loss was then assigned a specific weight to help the model learn the discriminative disease properties associated with each patch-label pair. The network, trained using loss reweighting was subsequently used to extract features from the patches.

LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) was used to encode the weighted patch feature sequences and create a comprehensive representation of the features. The effectiveness of the proposed method was validated through tests on this dataset, as well as on other publicly available datasets.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In plant disease detection, being able to recognize the illnesses on the leaves of plants is the main point. The three phases of the entire cycle are pre-processing, feature extraction, and classification. The noise from the image will be filtered in the pre-processing phase. Machine learning and deep learning, as key components of artificial intelligence, are frequently utilized for classification tasks. The framework devised for detecting plants disorders leverages transfer learning by integrating VGG16 with CNN. The various stages of this model are described in detail below.

1) *Input image and pre-processing*: The input image is initially processed by a Gaussian filter that more compellingly brings down the noise, while accuracy of the image is maintained. This is a smoothing filter that reduces the blurriness and eliminates the smallest image details. It is characterized as a part of the impulse response of the Gaussian function which is indicative of the probability distribution of the noise. The filter, by staying uniform, linear, and low-pass, resolves the Gaussian noise efficiently, and it is represented by a Gaussian function with a single standard deviation.

2) *Segmentation*: To change the default, adjust the template as follows. This work makes use of snake segmentation to isolate specific parts of the image. Inspired by the raster scan approach, this method ensures extensive coverage of the image's edges. The active contour model, integral to this technique, initializes a parameterized contour curve within the image space and defines an energy functional. This functional characterizes the region's shape through a combination of internal and external energy. Internal energy is influenced by properties of the curve, such as curvature and length, while external energy is derived from the image's features. By minimizing this energy functional, the initial contour curve $(s) = (x(s), y(s), s \in [0, 1])$ progressively adapts to align with the target area's boundary under the interplay of internal and external constraints.

$$E(C) = \int_0^1 \alpha E_{int}(C(s)) + E_{img}(C(s)) + \gamma E_{con}(C(s)) ds \quad \dots (1)$$

The energy function in the Snake active contour model consists of three components: E_{img} , E_{con} . The image energy (E_{img}) is defined based on specific target features, such as edges, to guide the curve towards the desired region. The constrained energy (E_{con}) accounts for geometric factors like curve length and curvature. A key advantage of this model is its ability to effectively integrate geometric constraints, enabling the extraction of smooth and closed boundaries, even with lower-quality images. However, the method has limitations, particularly its sensitivity to the initial contour. The position, shape, and number of control points in the initial contour must be appropriately chosen to achieve optimal results.

3) *Classification*: To predict the type of disease, this work applies transfer learning approach, combining VGG16 and ConvNet models. VGG16 serves as the base architecture, providing foundational feature extraction, while the ConvNet model is applied on top for training and fine-tuning.

Fig.2. VGG16 Model Architecture

Below are the key specifications of the VGG16 model:

- The VGG16 signifies the 16 layers with learnable weights. The architecture includes thirteen convolutional layers, five max-pooling layers, and three dense layers, totalling 21 layers, of which only 16 are weight layers with trainable parameters.
- VGG16 accepts an input tensor of size 224x224 with 3 RGB channels.
- A distinctive feature of VGG16 is its simplicity, achieved by utilizing 3x3 convolutional filters with a stride of 1 and consistent padding. Max-pooling layers use 2x2 filters with a stride of 2
- The convolutional and max-pooling layers are systematically arranged throughout the architecture.
- The Conv-1 layer contains 64 filters, Conv-2 has 128 filters, Conv-3 includes 256 filters, and Conv-4 and Conv-5 each have 512 filters.
- After the convolutional layers, there are three fully connected (FC) layers: the first two contain 4096 channels each, while the third layer, designed for 1000-way classification in ILSVRC, has 1000 channels. The output classification is performed by the final layer known as SoftMax layer.

Fig.3. Proposed Transfer Learning Model

IV. RESULT & DISCUSSION

Python is a versatile software that emphasizes ease of reading, dynamic semantics, and object-oriented traits. Python, as a scripting language, integrates different elements and accelerates the development of applications. With its straight forward syntax, Python promotes modularity and code reuse through support for modules and packages, which helps reduce maintenance costs. Additionally, the Python interpreter and its comprehensive standard library are freely available in both source and binary formats across most major platforms. Applications like GIMP, Inkscape, Blender, and Autodesk Maya leverage the Python API to extend their utility.

A. Dataset Description

The model that has been developed is assessed with the Plant Village dataset, a publicly accessible resource that provides detailed information about several plants and their connected diseases. The dataset covers the images where each is labelled for a specific disease type.

Fig.4. Input Image

Fig.5. Class Distribution

The dataset depicted in Figure 5 includes four classes, namely cedar apple rust, black rot, apple scab, and healthy. The distribution of the classes is represented as percentage.

Fig.6. Training and Test data

Figure 6 depicts the distribution of test and train data in percentage. The training data accounts for 80%, while the test data makes up 20%.

Fig.7. Model Training Information

Figure 7 depicts the model’s training and loss. As per this figure, the devised framework obtains 96% of training accuracy.

Fig.8. Confusion Matrix

Figure 8 depicts the testing the devised framework on the test data. There are four values (true positive, true negative, false positive and false negative) plotted on the confusion matrix.

B. Result Analysis

- Accuracy: One metric that is very commonly used to judge how good a program is accuracy. It is the number of correctly classified samples from the whole number of the samples. In the form of a mathematical equation, it is expressed as follows:

$$A_i = \frac{t}{n} \cdot 100$$

Here, t refers to the number of samples that have been correctly classified, and n denotes the overall samples.

- Precision: Precision defines how many true positive cases have been accurately predicted among the overall predicted positive cases

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$$

- Recall: Recall is a performance metric that measures the proportion of actual positive cases correctly identified as positive by the model. It indicates how effectively the positive prediction rule (+P) captures all the true positive cases.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$$

Table 1 represents a comparison of the CNN, Resnet 50, Bidirectional LSTM and Proposed model in the perspective of accuracy, precision, and recall. The values for these measurements are provided as a percentage of the whole.

TABLE 1. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
CNN Model	90	90	89
Resnet50	92.5	92	93
Bidirectional LSTM	88	88	88
Proposed Model	98.5	97	97

Fig.9. Performance Analysis

Figure 9 shows a comparison of the proposed model with the existing CNN, Resnet50, Bidirectional LSTM with proposed model. It is analyzed that proposed model achieves accuracy of 98 percent which is approximately 5 percent higher than the existing models.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of this study is to identify plant diseases by the plant leaves analysis. In the past, plant disease detection was conducted manually via the use of a microscope, which was an inefficient way for the identification of large-scale diseases due to its impracticality. However, with the advent of digital image processing and machine learning algorithms, plant pathologists can now detect diseases from digital images of plant leaves. The presented scheme exploits a voting-based architecture in conjunction with digital image processing methods for disease detection. Digital cameras have the capability to capture images, and image processing helps extract relevant features. Also, a transfer learning model is employed in this work for the plant disease detection. In the model, the accuracy of the diagnosis is up to 98%, which is approximately 8% higher than existent models.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. D. Khirade and A. B. Patil, "Plant Disease Detection Using Image Processing," 2015 International Conference on Computing Communication Control and Automation, Pune, India, 2015, pp. 768-771, doi: 10.1109/ICCUBEA.2015.153.
- [2] J.P. Shah, H.B. Prajapati and V.K. Dabhi, "A survey on detection and classification of rice plant diseases," 2016 IEEE International Conference on Current Trends in Advanced Computing (ICCTAC), Bangalore, India, 2016, pp. 1-8, doi: 10.1109/ICCTAC.2016.7567333.
- [3] R. Zhou, S. Kaneko, F. Tanaka, M. Kayamori and M. Shimizu, "Early Detection and Continuous Quantization of Plant Disease Using Template Matching and Support Vector Machine Algorithms," 2013 First International Symposium on Computing and Networking, Matsuyama, Japan, 2013, pp. 300-304, doi: 10.1109/CANDAR.2013.52.
- [4] S. Zhang and C. Zhang, "Orthogonal Locally Discriminant Projection for Classification of Plant Leaf Diseases," 2013 Ninth International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Security, Emeishan, China, 2013, pp. 241-245, doi: 10.1109/CIS.2013.57.
- [5] H. Hashim, M. A. Haron, F. N. Osman and S. A. M. Al Junid, "Classification of Rubber Tree Leaf Disease Using Spectrometer," 2010 Fourth Asia International Conference on Mathematical/Analytical Modelling and Computer Simulation, Kota Kinabalu, Malaysia, 2010, pp. 302-306, doi: 10.1109/AMS.2010.67.
- [6] V. Singh, Varsha and A. K. Misra, "Detection of unhealthy region of plant leaves using image processing and genetic algorithm," 2015

- International Conference on Advances in Computer Engineering and Applications, Ghaziabad, India, 2015, pp. 1028-1032, doi: 10.1109/ICACEA.2015.7164858.
- [7] M. Jhuria, A. Kumar and R. Borse, "Image processing for smart farming: Detection of disease and fruit grading," 2013 IEEE Second International Conference on Image Information Processing (ICIIP-2013), Shimla, India, 2013, pp. 521-526, doi: 10.1109/ICIIP.2013.6707647.
- [8] G. Zellnig, S. Möstl and B. Zechmann, "Rapid immune histochemical diagnosis of tobacco mosaic virus disease by microwave-assisted plant sample preparation," in *Microscopy*, vol. 62, no. 5, pp. 547-553, Oct. 2013, doi: 10.1093/jmicro/dfi022.
- [9] P. Revathi and M. Hemalatha, "Classification of cotton leaf spot diseases using image processing edge detection techniques," 2012 International Conference on Emerging Trends in Science, Engineering and Technology (INCOSSET), Tiruchirappalli, India, 2012, pp. 169-173, doi: 10.1109/INCOSSET.2012.6513900.
- [10] D. Ashourloo, H. Aghighi, A. A. Matkan, M.R. Mobasheri and A.M. Rad, "An Investigation into Machine Learning Regression Techniques for the Leaf Rust Disease Detection Using Hyperspectral Measurement," in *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, vol. 9, no. 9, pp. 4344-4351, Sept. 2016, doi: 10.1109/JSTARS.2016.2575360.
- [11] N. Schor, A. Bechar, T. Ignat, A. Dombrovsky, Y. Eladand, S. Berman, "Robotic Disease Detection in Greenhouses: Combined Detection of Powdery Mildew and Tomato Spotted Wilt Virus," in *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 354-360, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1109/LRA.2016.2518214.
- [12] P. Revathi and M. Hemalatha, "Advance computing enrichment evaluation of cotton leaf spot disease detection using Image Edge detection," 2012 Third International Conference on Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT'12), Coimbatore, India, 2012, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICCCNT.2012.6395903.
- [13] K. R. Gavhale, U. Gawande and K. O. Hajari, "Unhealthy region of citrus leaf detection using image processing techniques," International Conference for Convergence for Technology-2014, Pune, India, 2014, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/I2CT.2014.7092035.
- [14] E. Borges, A.P. Matos, J.M. Cardoso, C. Correia, T. Vasconcelos and N. Gomes, "Early detection and monitoring of plant diseases by Bioelectric Impedance Spectroscopy," 2012 IEEE 2nd Portuguese Meeting in Bioengineering (ENBENG), Coimbra, Portugal, 2012, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ENBENG.2012.6331377.
- [15] J. Kuruvilla, D. Sukumaran, A. Sankar and S. P. Joy, "A review on image processing and image segmentation," 2016 International Conference on Data Mining and Advanced Computing (SAPIENCE), Ernakulam, India, 2016, pp. 198-203, doi: 10.1109/SAPIENCE.2016.7684170.
- [16] J. Chen, J. Chen and Y. A. Nanehkar, "Using deep transfer learning for image-based plant disease identification," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 173, pp. 14-25, 6 April 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.compag.2020.105393.
- [17] M. Sardogan, A. Tuncer and Y. Ozen, "Plant Leaf Disease Detection and Classification Based on CNN with LVQ Algorithm," 2018 3rd International Conference on Computer Science and Engineering (UBMK), Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2018, pp. 382-385, doi: 10.1109/UBMK.2018.8566635.
- [18] A. Adedaja, P.A. Owolawi and T. Mapayi, "Deep Learning Based on NASNet for Plant Disease Recognition Using Leave Images," 2019 International Conference on Advances in Big Data, Computing and Data Communication Systems (icABCD), Winterton, South Africa, 2019, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICABCD.2019.8851029.
- [19] P. Jiang, Y. Chen, B. Liu, D. He and C. Liang, "Real-Time Detection of Apple Leaf Diseases Using Deep Learning Approach Based on Improved Convolutional Neural Networks," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 59069-59080, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2914929.
- [20] P. Wspanialy and M. Moussa, "A detection and severity estimation system for generic diseases of tomato greenhouse plants," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 178, pp. 69-75, 2 September 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.compag.2020.105701.
- [21] Z. Iqbal, M. A. Khan and K. Javed, "An automated detection and classification of citrus plant diseases using image processing techniques: A review," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 153, pp. 12-32, October 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.compag.2018.07.032.
- [22] A. Waheed, M. Goyal and H.M. Pandey, "An optimized dense

- [23] S. Mishra, R. Sachan and D. Rajpal, "Deep Convolutional Neural Network based Detection System for Real-time Corn Plant Disease Recognition", *Procedia Computer Science*, vol.167, pp.2003-2010, 16 April 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2020.03.236.
- [24] Z. Lin et al., "A Unified Matrix-Based Convolutional Neural Network for Fine-Grained Image Classification of Wheat Leaf Diseases," *In IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 11570-11590, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2891739.
- [25] E.C. Tetila et al., "Automatic Recognition of Soybean Leaf Diseases Using UAV Images and Deep Convolutional Neural Networks," *In IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, Vol.17,no.5,pp.903-907, May 2020, doi:10.1109/LGRS.2019.2932385.
- [26] X. Liu, W. Min, S. Mei, L. Wang and S. Jiang, "Plant Disease Recognition: A Large-Scale Benchmark Dataset and a Visual Region and Loss Reweighting Approach," *In IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 30, pp. 2003-2015, 2021, doi: 10.1109/TIP.2021.3049334.